

Beyond Relativity

Transcendence with Time Dilation for Time Travel

Rishabh Garg and Anuja Vyas

Birla Institute of Technology & Science, Pilani - 403726 India
Institute for Excellence in Higher Education, Bhopal - 462016 India

Abstract

The concept of time travel, allows movement across different points in time, and has been a subject of extensive debate. This intriguing topic continues to pose many unsolved riddles that calls for further exploration. This article revisits the well-established theory of relativity, offering a new vision to time travel by integrating ancient insights into dimension travel through consciousness. It introduces the idea of Transcendental Meditative Travel, which could address existing paradoxes and provide a new insight to the quest of time travel. The article also distinguishes between the much-discussed hypothetical time travel and the currently investigated time travel via time dilation.

Key phrases

Astral travel, Theory of Relativity, Time dilation, Time Dimension, Time travel, Transcendental meditation.

Introduction

Space and time have always fascinated people. It was supposed to be unrelated and absolute until, the Theory of Relativity incorporating two interrelated theories were proposed by Albert Einstein. Einstein published Special relativity in 1905, which applies to all physical phenomena in the absence of gravity. Ten years later, in 1915, he presented General Relativity, which explains connection of gravity to other natural forces. According to the general theory of relativity, massive objects cause a distortion in the fabric of space and time that are experienced as gravity.

Ab initio, Einstein's concepts did not enthrall much scientific interest. However, in 1949, Kurt Gödel solved Einstein's general relativity equations, describing a gyrating universe ^[1]. This sparked wider scientific acceptance of time travel. The idea of time travel has since become popular, thanks to science fiction in movies, TV shows, comic books, novels, and other media. People are fascinated by the idea of traveling back in time, even if they do not fully understand it.

Time travel can be simply defined as the hypothetical act of moving into the past or future. It is important to note that real time travel remains largely theoretical. One practical approach to time travel is called Time Dilation, a concept introduced by Albert Einstein. It refers to the difference in elapsed time between two events ^[2]. In essence, it is a technique

that causes the time to appear slower or faster than it actually elapses. This approach has its own limitations, which are discussed at length in this article.

However, before exploring ideas and applications related to time travel, it is essential to understand the enigmatic and implied concepts.

Time Travel and the Associated Paradoxes

Time travel is an idea of moving into the past or future. While this concept sounds simple, it is quite furtive and full of unknowns. One big problem is that we do not fully understand how the universe works. There are countless questions that continue to baffle scholarly minds: Does time travel really exist? Is it actually possible to travel into the past or future? If someone does travel through time and comes back, what kind of present will he return to -the one he had left; the one that others are experiencing; or a new one altogether? Time travel is an intriguing subject that captures the imagination of every commoner, but even experts find it mystic.

Time is not absolute; it's relative. According to Einstein's theory of relativity, different people can experience time differently. So, how could time travel be possible if time itself is not absolute? Time travel can happen in two ways: going to the past or heading to the future.

Time Travel in Past

Traveling back in time is uncertain due to several unrequited questions. If we are in the 'present', this means the 'past' has already happened, leading to the current moment. Since time is not absolute and varies, we need to know where it has gone and how much time has passed between now and then to travel back accurately. In simple terms, to build a time machine to travel into the past, we must determine the exact moment and place to reach.

Moreover, there are some logical problems to consider before attempting time travel. One well-known example is the 'Grandfather Paradox'. Imagine a time traveller goes back in time and kills his grandfather before his father is born. If this happened, how could the time traveller exist in the first place? This paradox highlights a fundamental problem with the concept of time travel ^[3].

Time Travel in Future

Traveling into the future is even more uncertain and seems impossible according to our present state of knowledge. It involves many aspects that might be too complex for us to understand right now. Imagine you are playing cricket with your friends. Your friends won the toss and chose to field. As a batter, when the ball is bowled to you, you have two main outcomes to consider: the ball either rolls on the ground past the fielders or gets caught by one of them. You cannot control what the fielders do; you can only hit the ball. If you hit it hard, it might go out of the field, and you may get runs. If not, you could be bold, caught or run out.

Fig. 1: Demonstrating the two possible outcomes that can only occur after the batter strikes the ball, depicting the dependence of future on present actions or decisions.

This shows that the future does not exist until the present has happened. In other words, the decisions made in the 'now' shape the future.

Likewise, making a change in the universe might upset its balance. The universe would then try to fix this imbalance, either by reversing it, stabilizing the repeated activities within the same time frame, or through some other cryptic way beyond our understanding. Unfortunately, no one knows exactly how the universe maintains its balance.

It is reasonable to believe that everything in the universe happens for a reason and follows a pattern. If the universe were random, it would not make sense that the earth is part of it, or that gravitational forces consistently keep planets in orbit around the sun, or that blackholes trap light with their immense gravity. You do not randomly leap and land on the earth and other times you merely fly around (as in space). This is due to a predetermined pattern rather than being a chance occurrence, which has allowed science and technology to advance to such great heights. Regrettably, it will take a very long time for humans to fully grasp how the universe functions.

Time Dimension

When a 3D object casts a shadow on a flat surface, its shape looks distorted. Time is often considered as the fourth dimension. So, if something from the fourth-dimension casts a shadow, it would lose one of its dimensions. Similarly, if a human being, who exists in three

dimensions, tried to travel through the fourth dimension (time) without changing physically, he would become warped or distorted. Precisely, the universe resists changes that could make it askew or unstable. These chances make human time travel very unlikely.

Time Dilation

Time dilation is considered the most widely accepted and theoretically possible way to travel through time. It means that time passes at different rates for different people, depending on how fast they are moving or where they are in a gravitational field ^[4]. This concept comes from Einstein's theory of relativity, which says that space and time are not separate but intertwined as spacetime.

Time dilation happens either by moving through a high velocity like the speed of light because time passes slower for the person travelling with the speed of light relative to another person. For example, if someone travels in a spacecraft at the speed of light, eight days might pass for them, while eighty days pass for someone on Earth. This means the person in the spacecraft has effectively travelled into the future compared to those on Earth. This is called relative velocity time dilation. However, moving equal to or faster than the speed of light is currently unattainable because it requires extremely high energy and advanced technology that we do not have yet.

Traveling close to massive object, like a black hole, is another way to dilate time. Black holes have such strong gravity that they pull everything in, even light, making it impossible

Fig 2: Experience of time dilation: Visual depiction of a spaceship orbiting a black hole.

for anything to escape ^[5]. This intense gravity causes time to slow down near the black hole, a phenomenon called gravitational time dilation. If someone were to go in a circle around a black hole such that it is not pulled into it (we know, time is very slow there), he would travel ideally into the future because he would travel a large distance within the given time-frame. Given that the rate to get in future is twice than the normal rate, it implies that if we ride in the spaceship for 5 minutes around the black hole, it would be equal to 10 minutes on Earth ^[2].

The methods mentioned might seem simple, but are not practically feasible, at least for next few decades. Even if one of these techniques were ever proven possible, it would only permit travel to the future and not back in time. Time travel, as we understand it, involves time dilation. However, this does not match the fantasies that science fiction movies have instilled in individuals, where people can hop back and forth through time.

Transcendental Meditative Time Travel

An interesting twist on time travel is 'Transcendental Meditative Travel'. Unlike the erstwhile methods, which essentially served as impediments that prevented people from traveling through time, or the fourth dimension, Transcendental meditative travel offers a pragmatic way to journey through time. This approach helps address the issues faced by earlier methods.

Transcendental meditative travel can be conceptualized as the mind or consciousness moving through time. It is a singular concept with a spiritual component. Ancient Hindu scriptures like the Vedas, Puranas, and Epics, penned centuries ago, are still relevant today, much like Einstein's theory of relativity. These ancient theories touch on ideas like gravity, age, time dilation, and exclusive spacecraft technology that enable them to travel light years between planets ^[6].

In a similar vein, the historical approach to time travel is based on the belief that the sages from the Indian subcontinent could foresee the future and traverse time and space effortlessly, transcending the usual precincts of past, present, and future. They could do so by focusing their entire energy on their minds, which enable them to travel across time simply by being physically present in a certain location. They achieve this through 'siddhis or supernatural powers gained through deep meditation ^[7]. This phenomenon can be compared with the idea of 'astral travel or astral projection' which is defined as the ability of a person's spirit to explore far-off places. Astral travel can also be understood as the detachment of one's consciousness from the physical body. There are evidences of astral travel which describes it as 'out-of-body experiences (OBEs)' ^[8] ^[9].

Although Transcendental meditative travel is feasible, it demands a high level of attention, so not everyone can master it. To reach this state, one must concentrate deeply, particularly on the *ajna chakra*, located between the eyebrows, often referred to as the 'third eye'. The *ajna chakra* is believed to be linked to the highest state of awareness, one of the seven energy centres (chakras), along the spine. The *ajna chakra* governs mental clarity, consciousness, decision-making, and an individual's interaction with the natural world ^[10].

Fig 3: Alignment of the Ajna chakra with the Pre-frontal cortex.

From a scientific standpoint, the human brain supports this contention. The brain is divided into frontal lobe, parietal lobe, temporal lobe, and occipital lobe ^[11], with the prefrontal cortex of the frontal lobe playing a decisive role. Interestingly, the location of the ajna chakra aligns with this region. The prefrontal cortex is recognized as a higher-order centre responsible for complex cognitive functions such as decision-making and problem-solving ^[12]. It also processes spatial relationships between the self and the surrounding, reinforcing the connection between the mind and the external world ^[13].

By activating the *ajna chakra* - essentially engaging the prefrontal cortex - one can suppress distractions and achieve a focused mental state. This level of concentrated attention allows practitioners to transcend normal sensory experiences, potentially exploring dimensions beyond the immediate physical world. A study by neuroscientists at MIT identified a brain circuit that helps suppress irrelevant sensory input and background noise, regulated by the prefrontal cortex. This circuit blocks unnecessary information from reaching the thalamus, the brain's sensory gateway, allowing the mind to focus solely on relevant stimuli ^[14].

Therefore, while the two physical eyes observe the past and the present, the third eye can take you into the future ^[15]. Neuroimaging studies, such as those using fMRI and EEG, have shown increased brain activity during meditation in regions associated with attention, self-regulation, and self-control, primarily within the prefrontal cortex ^[16]. Thus, Transcendental meditative travel overcomes the drawbacks of earlier methods that were extremely persistent, and thus, it does offer a novel way to explore beyond the usual time limits ^[17].

In principle, Einstein showed that massless particles like photons can only reach the speed of light. Being massless, the human mind or consciousness can match or even surpass the speed of light, eliminating the chances of creating subverts in the past or future, like travel through the fourth dimension (time) or run into a grandfather paradox. Hence, this approach can be considered as one of the potential breakthroughs to time travel, as it would avoid causing problems with time, offering a possible pathway to time travel.

Suppose, if the distance between any hypothetical point 'a' in the universe and 'Earth' is 1 billion light years ($d = 1 \text{ bly}$), then the light emanating from 'a' will take 1 billion years ($t = 1 \text{ by}$) to reach Earth. This means that when we see something from 'a' today, we actually see it as it was on Earth 1 billion years ago ($t = -1 \text{ by}$), because it takes time for light to travel such a cosmic distance from Earth to point 'a'.

Now, imagine that through transcendental meditation, someone on Earth projects his consciousness onto the same point 'a' in real time (say, $t = 1 \text{ sec}$). By doing so, he will see 'a' as it is today, and at the same time, he will also see the past of Earth as it appeared 1 billion years ago ($t = -1 \text{ by}$). This means that such a person, by focusing his awareness on that distant point, can theoretically observe life forms or events occurred on earth, such as the era when dinosaurs roamed our planet, a billion years ago. This is because it takes 1 billion years for those events on Earth to travel the cosmic distance to 'a'.

Similarly, the events, object or structures that exist at point 'a' today, will become visible on Earth 1 billion years from now, as it takes that long for the light to carry the image to reach Earth.

Fig 4: Mechanism of transcendental travel.

Conclusion

In this article, the authors attempted to explore time travel from a fresh and de novo perspective. Though time travel and time dilation are related, they are not the same and cannot be used interchangeably. Firstly, it is important to understand the true nature of time and why time exists? Also, there are a number of queries that need to be resolved before arriving at any conclusion or theory. The concept itself is mysterious and involves many unexplained phenomena, so it would be imprudent to reject any idea that may help achieve the objective. While there are various ways to think about time dilation, the idea of Transcendental meditative travel could offer new insights into time travel and expand our understanding of consciousness and the human mind, which itself is quite mystical.

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